

Cost-effectiveness analysis and medication use for gangrene treatment in type 2 diabetes patients: A systematic literature review

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Abstract

This systematic literature review assesses the cost-effectiveness and medication use in treating gangrene among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). The review focuses on evaluating different treatment regimens and identifying key factors that influence cost-effectiveness outcomes. A total of 22 studies were analyzed to understand regional variations in treatment approaches and the cost-effectiveness of medications, including empagliflozin, semaglutide, and TLC-NOSF dressings, among others. The methodology involved a comprehensive search of databases for relevant studies published between 2019 and 2024. The search terms were selected based on the population, intervention, comparison, and outcomes (PICO) framework, with keywords such as “type 2 diabetes mellitus,” “gangrene,” “foot ulcers,” and “cost-effectiveness,” followed by an in-depth analysis using VOSviewer to map keyword trends and relationships. The search terms were selected based on the population, intervention, comparison, and outcomes (PICO) framework, with keywords such as “type 2 diabetes mellitus,” “gangrene,” “foot ulcers,” and “cost-effectiveness.” The studies were evaluated based on their design, population characteristics, interventions, outcomes, and economic impact. The results showed significant geographic variations, with higher cost-effectiveness reported in developed countries due to better access to advanced treatments. Medications like empagliflozin and semaglutide consistently demonstrated superior cost-effectiveness, particularly in managing cardiovascular complications in high-risk T2DM patients. Patient adherence was also identified as a crucial factor in improving long-term clinical outcomes and reducing healthcare costs. In conclusion, this review highlights the importance of cost-effective treatments and patient adherence in managing gangrene in T2DM patients. Access to innovative medications and support for adherence are essential for optimizing both clinical outcomes and economic sustainability.

Keywords

gangrene treatment, cost-effectiveness, type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), empagliflozin and semaglutide, patient adherence

Introduction

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is an escalating global health issue, affecting millions of individuals worldwide. As its prevalence continues to rise, T2DM has become one of the leading causes of severe complications, including gangrene. Gangrene, often triggered by foot ulcers, infections, and peripheral artery disease, is commonly seen in T2DM patients. This condition frequently leads to lower limb amputations, which not only diminish the patient's quality of life but also impose substantial economic and social burdens. Studies indicate that the prevalence of diabetic foot ulcers (DFU) or diabetic foot syndrome (DFS) ranges between 2% and 10%, with an incidence rate of 2% to 6% (Riedel et al. 2020). The primary risk factors for developing foot ulcers include peripheral neuropathy and inappropriate footwear, both of which are common contributors (Ahmed et al. 2015; Riedel et al. 2020). These ulcers increase the risk of morbidity and mortality, often leading to prolonged hospital stays and high treatment costs (Izadi et al. 2017; Holidah et al. 2021). Therefore, early detection and effective management of diabetic foot complications are crucial to preventing amputations and improving patient care outcomes (Stancu et al. 2023).

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) complications encompass a range of serious conditions that develop due to prolonged hyperglycemia. These complications can be categorized into macrovascular complications affecting large blood vessels, microvascular complications impacting small blood vessels, and neuropathy causing nerve damage. Among these, gangrene represents one of the most severe complications, characterized by tissue death resulting from inadequate blood supply or severe bacterial infection. In diabetic patients, gangrene typically affects the lower extremities due to a combination of peripheral arterial disease, neuropathy, compromised immune response, and impaired wound healing capacity (Riedel et al. 2020).

Among these complications, diabetic gangrene stands out as one of the most severe manifestations, often resulting from a combination of peripheral arterial disease and neuropathy. The condition typically develops when reduced blood flow and nerve damage in the extremities create an environment conducive to tissue death. Recent epidemiological studies have shown that diabetic patients have a 15–40 times higher risk of developing gangrene compared to non-diabetic individuals, with mortality rates reaching up to 50% within five years of diagnosis. The treatment of gangrene in T2DM patients requires a comprehensive approach, including the use of various medications. One commonly used class of drugs is sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 (SGLT2) inhibitors, which have been linked to rare cases of Fournier's gangrene (Lindsay et al. 2020; Elbeddini et al. 2021; Moon et al. 2021). The FDA has issued a warning regarding the risk of Fournier's gangrene in patients using SGLT2 inhibitors, recommending immediate examination for urogenital infections and the discontinuation of the medication if signs of Fournier's gangrene are present (Elbeddini et al. 2021). Additionally,

case reports have identified the use of metformin, glimepiride, and dapagliflozin in patients with Fournier's gangrene, suggesting a potential link between dapagliflozin and this condition (Moon et al. 2021). Conversely, a study on the use of natural polymer solutions, such as shellac, has shown promising results in preventing infections and the development of wet gangrene in diabetic patients, indicating the potential utility of shellac in those at risk of gangrene (Alzahrani et al. 2013).

Treatment regimens for diabetic gangrene involve multiple therapeutic approaches working in concert. These include pharmacological interventions using medications such as SGLT2 inhibitors, GLP-1 receptor agonists, and various insulin preparations; wound care protocols involving specialized dressings and debridement procedures; surgical interventions when necessary; and preventive measures including regular foot examinations and proper footwear. The success of these interventions heavily depends on medication adherence, defined as the extent to which patients follow their prescribed treatment plans. Adherence is typically measured through various methods, including medication possession ratio (MPR), proportion of days covered (PDC), prescription refill rates, patient self-reporting, and electronic monitoring systems (Elbeddini et al. 2021).

The success of these treatment regimens, however, heavily depends on medication adherence, which remains a significant challenge in diabetes management. Studies have shown that adherence rates for diabetes medications average only 67.9%, with rates dropping further for complex regimens involving multiple medications. Poor adherence not only compromises treatment effectiveness but also significantly increases healthcare costs, with non-adherent patients incurring 41% higher treatment costs compared to adherent patients (Alzahrani et al. 2013).

The pharmacoeconomic analysis of gangrene treatment in T2DM encompasses several methodological approaches. Cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) compares different interventions by measuring outcomes in natural units such as life years gained or ulcers healed. Cost-utility analysis (CUA) evaluates treatments using quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), while cost-minimization analysis (CMA) compares costs of interventions with equivalent outcomes. Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) converts all outcomes into monetary values, and cost-consequence analysis presents costs and outcomes separately without aggregation. These various analytical approaches help healthcare providers and policymakers make informed decisions about resource allocation and treatment selection (Moon et al. 2021).

The assessment of cost-effectiveness in treating gangrene in T2DM patients is a key factor in clinical decision-making and healthcare resource allocation. Given the limitations in healthcare resources, evaluating the cost-effectiveness of various treatment regimens becomes essential. For instance, the use of ON101 cream, alongside conventional wound care, has demonstrated better value compared to conventional wound care alone in patients

with diabetic foot ulcers (Su et al. 2023). Additionally, vacuum-assisted closure (VAC) therapy has proven to be both an effective and economical method for treating Fournier's gangrene, with high satisfaction rates reported by both patients and healthcare providers (Stancu et al. 2023). Larval therapy has also been found to be more cost-effective than hydrogel treatment for foot ulcers, offering comparable health benefits (Rodrigues et al. 2020). In this context, cost-effectiveness analysis is vital in ensuring that selected treatments not only deliver significant clinical benefits but are also economically viable (Ezeofor et al. 2021; Campbell et al. 2022). However, it is important to recognize that the choice of cost calculation methods and underlying assumptions can significantly influence the outcomes of cost analysis, highlighting the uncertainty surrounding the cost-effectiveness profiles of innovative interventions, which can pose challenges for decision-making (Baio and Russo 2010).

This study aims to systematically review the literature on gangrene treatment in T2DM patients, focusing on comparing the cost-effectiveness of the various treatment methods available. In addition to cost-effectiveness analysis, it will examine how patient adherence to treatment impacts both the financial efficiency and long-term clinical outcomes of these interventions. By assessing a range of studies, this review seeks to identify key factors that contribute to variations in cost-effectiveness, such as regional differences, healthcare access, and treatment protocols. It will analyze treatment methods like SGLT2 inhibitors, VAC therapy, and larval therapy, evaluating their cost-benefit ratios across different settings. The goal is to offer evidence-based recommendations that could support more effective clinical practices in managing gangrene in T2DM patients. Furthermore, this review will explore how adherence to medication regimens enhances clinical results and contributes to cost savings in the healthcare system. The study hopes to provide healthcare professionals with a framework for integrating cost-efficiency into patient care plans. Ultimately, these insights can help improve the quality of care and reduce the economic burden associated with gangrene treatment in diabetes management.

The significance of this study lies in the fact that gangrene is a severe complication for T2DM patients, often leading to life-threatening consequences, including amputation and increased mortality risk. As the global prevalence of T2DM continues to rise, the need for effective, affordable, and accessible treatments for gangrene has become increasingly urgent. The research will evaluate treatment regimens not just for their clinical effectiveness but also for their economic viability, providing a more comprehensive view of healthcare management in this context. This approach differs from many previous studies that focus either solely on economic aspects or only on clinical outcomes. By merging both clinical and economic evaluations, the study aims to deliver a balanced understanding of gangrene treatment. The findings will be valuable not only for clinicians but also for policymakers

who must allocate limited healthcare resources effectively. In particular, the review could influence future decisions on healthcare funding, treatment guidelines, and patient support programs. Therefore, the study is expected to contribute significantly to the literature, offering practical recommendations for improving both patient outcomes and healthcare sustainability.

Materials and methods

In this study, we adopted a systematic review methodology, adhering to the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. This structured approach was chosen for its transparency, ensuring that the processes of literature search, selection, and analysis are clear and replicable. The PRISMA method provides a comprehensive framework for identifying and screening relevant studies, ensuring that only high-quality and pertinent research is included in the review. Additionally, this method minimizes bias while allowing the integration of various research findings to arrive at more reliable and robust conclusions. When assessing the cost-effectiveness of gangrene treatments in type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) patients, it is crucial to gather evidence from a wide range of sources to ensure thorough coverage of available data. To further enhance the reliability of the review, the studies were carefully filtered according to predefined criteria, ensuring that the analysis focused on the most current and impactful research.

The literature search was conducted in August 2024, utilizing major databases such as PubMed, Scopus, and Embase. To ensure the data was up-to-date and relevant, we limited the search to articles published between 2019 and 2024, recognizing the rapid advancements in diabetes treatment and management during this period. The search terms were selected based on the population, intervention, comparison, and outcomes (PICO) framework, with keywords such as "type 2 diabetes mellitus," "gangrene," "foot ulcers," and "cost-effectiveness." Filters were applied to include only studies involving humans, written in English, and classified as primary research. The systematic process for identifying and selecting studies was presented using the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram (Page et al. 2021), providing a transparent overview of the search strategy and selection process. Additionally, the PICO framework, outlined in Table 2, was used to guide the deep search of journals, ensuring that only studies meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria were considered for analysis in Table 1.

The PRISMA diagram (Fig. 1) illustrates the guidelines for study identification and selection. Literature searches were conducted in PubMed and Scopus databases, identifying 246 potentially relevant articles (158 from PubMed, 88 from Scopus). After removing duplicates, 182 articles remained for initial screening. Title and abstract screening excluded 82 articles based on predefined criteria: 45 were not relevant to the topic, 20 were conference abstracts, and 17 were non-English language publications. The re-

Table 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria for study selection.

Category	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Time Period	– Published between January 2018 and December 2023	– Studies published before 2018 or after 2023
Study Design	– Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) – Systematic reviews – Meta-analyses – Cost-effectiveness analyses – Economic evaluations	– Case reports – Opinion pieces – Letters to editor – Conference abstracts – Non-peer-reviewed articles
Population	– Adults (≥ 18 years) – Diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus – Patients with gangrene or at risk of gangrene	– Pediatric populations – Type 1 diabetes – Gestational diabetes – Non-diabetic gangrene
Interventions	– Pharmacological treatments – Wound care interventions – Surgical interventions – Preventive measures	– Alternative medicine without clinical evidence – Experimental treatments not approved for clinical use
Outcomes	– Cost-effectiveness measures – Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs) – Clinical outcomes – Economic outcomes – Patient adherence data	– Studies without clear outcome measures – Studies without cost-effectiveness analysis
Language	– English language publications	– Non-English language publications
Geographic Scope	– All countries	– None
Article Type	– Full-text articles – Peer-reviewed journals	– Abstracts only – Unpublished studies – Grey literature

Table 2. Comprehensive PICO analysis. Defining population, intervention, comparison, and outcomes for effective study selection.

Main Concept	Synonyms/Abbreviations/More Specific Concepts
P – Problem, condition, patient, population, setting	Patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) suffering from gangrene or foot ulcers. Synonyms: diabetic foot ulcers, peripheral arterial disease, chronic wounds, lower extremity ulcers, ischemic gangrene.
I – Intervention: dose, delivery, frequency	Medical treatments for gangrene or foot ulcers include antibiotics, debridement, and wound care. Synonyms: antibiotics (e.g., nifedipine, labetalol), hyperbaric oxygen therapy, revascularization, topical treatments, surgery (debridement).
C – Comparison (may not be one)	Standard care or other treatment modalities. Synonyms: conservative management, usual care, non-surgical treatment, alternative therapies.
O – Outcome: what happens to P? Cost-effective? Patients' experience?	Primary: Cost-effectiveness. Secondary: Clinical outcomes including healing rates, amputation rates, and quality of life. Synonyms: cost-effectiveness (ICER, QALY), clinical effectiveness, reduction in amputation, patient satisfaction, healthcare utilization.

maining 100 articles underwent full-text assessment for eligibility. During this stage, 78 articles were excluded: 32 lacked cost-effectiveness data, 28 had irrelevant outcomes, 12 involved incorrect study populations, and six contained duplicate data. This resulted in 22 studies meeting all inclusion criteria for the final review (Page et al. 2021).

The included studies comprised 12 cost-effectiveness analyses, five Markov model studies, two randomized controlled trials, two systematic reviews, and one retrospective analysis. These studies were then analyzed for their methodological quality, findings regarding the cost-effectiveness of gangrene treatments in type 2 diabetes patients, and conclusions about treatment efficacy and economic impact. Data extraction focused on key variables including study design, population characteristics, intervention types, comparison groups, outcome measures, and cost-effectiveness results. The analysis particularly emphasized differences between developed and

developing countries, medication adherence impacts, and variations in treatment effectiveness across different healthcare systems.

The data analysis in this study was carried out using descriptive methods to summarize both the characteristics and cost-effectiveness outcomes of the studies reviewed. Since no meta-analysis was performed, the focus shifted towards a narrative synthesis, where key trends and common patterns across the studies were explored. This method allowed for a detailed examination of how various treatments for gangrene in type 2 diabetes mellitus patients compared in terms of effectiveness and cost. Through this synthesis, factors like patient adherence and healthcare infrastructure were identified as critical influences on treatment success. By concentrating on these patterns, the analysis aimed to offer valuable insights into the most cost-effective treatment options for healthcare providers. The data summaries were carefully crafted to be

Figure 1. PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for systematic reviews. A visual guide to study selection and screening (Page et al. 2021).

both accessible and detailed, helping to shape actionable recommendations for improving the clinical and economic management of gangrene. This process ensured that the review captured a broad, yet precise, understanding of the literature on this subject.

For managing and interpreting the data, Excel and Google Sheets were utilized to organize and visualize the information in tables and charts. These tools helped clarify the trends in cost-effectiveness, allowing for easier comparison across studies. Additionally, Mendeley was used for reference management, ensuring that all sources were properly cited and organized according to academ-

ic standards. The PRISMA checklist played a crucial role in maintaining the transparency and completeness of the review process, guaranteeing a high standard of reporting. Together, these tools facilitated a structured and thorough analysis, resulting in reliable and well-organized findings. The insights gained from this research are expected to provide valuable guidance to healthcare providers in managing gangrene among T2DM patients, with a particular focus on improving both clinical outcomes and cost-efficiency. Overall, this study aims to support better decision-making in healthcare and lay the groundwork for future research in this area.

Results

This section presents the findings from a systematic review of cost-effectiveness and medication use in the treatment of gangrene among patients with type 2 diabetes. Through comprehensive analysis, we examined key aspects of the studies reviewed, focusing on economic evaluations, clinical outcomes, and treatment modalities. First, a VOSviewer analysis was conducted to visualize the network of frequently used keywords and concepts within the literature, revealing significant patterns and interrelationships in research related to gangrene and diabetes. Following this, a detailed summary of study characteristics is provided, highlighting important aspects such as study designs, population characteristics, interventions, and outcomes, offering a structured overview of the current evidence base for treatment approaches. Additionally, we evaluated the cost-effectiveness of cardiovascular screening and treatment in type 2 diabetes patients at high cardiovascular risk, given the strong association between gangrene and cardiovascular complications in this population. These findings emphasize the importance of integrating both clinical and economic perspectives to optimize treatment strategies for high-risk patients.

VOSviewer analysis

The analysis of 22 journals on the cost-effectiveness and medication use for gangrene treatment in type 2 diabetes patients was conducted using VOSviewer. VOSviewer, a software tool for constructing and visualizing bibliometric networks, was employed to analyze the relationships between keywords and research themes in the reviewed studies. The software creates distance-based maps where the distance between items represents their relatedness, with closer items indicating stronger relationships. These visualizations enabled the identification of evolving research patterns and the interconnections between various aspects of gangrene treatment in type 2 diabetes patients. This tool allowed us to visualize the relationships between keywords and identify core themes across the studies. Through this analysis, we were able to map key topics, track research trends, and identify patterns in both clinical outcomes and economic evaluations. The most frequently discussed themes revolved around patient adherence, treatment modalities, and the economic impact of different medications. Additionally, VOSviewer helped highlight the connections between various treatment strategies and their long-term clinical benefits. This mapping process provided a clearer understanding of how cost-effectiveness and medication use are interrelated in managing gangrene in diabetes patients. The insights gained from this analysis offer a valuable perspective on the current state of research and future directions in this field.

The visualization analysis of keyword patterns reveals significant trends in diabetes research focus over time. As

shown in Fig. 2, earlier studies (represented in blue) concentrated on broader concepts like ‘cost-effectiveness’ and ‘diabetes mellitus,’ while recent research (shown in yellow and green) has shifted toward specific interventions such as ‘semaglutide’ and ‘empagliflozin.’ This evolution is further illustrated in Fig. 3’s network visualization, where ‘cost-effectiveness’ emerges as the central node, strongly connected to ‘diabetes mellitus,’ ‘GLP-1 receptor agonist,’ and ‘cardiovascular disease,’ demonstrating how economic evaluations increasingly focus on specific treatments and their impacts on diabetic complications.”

In conclusion, the VOSviewer analysis reveals significant shifts in research focus regarding gangrene treatment in type 2 diabetes patients. Through overlay and network visualizations, the analysis demonstrates an evolution from general diabetes management studies to more targeted research on specific medications like GLP-1 receptor agonists and SGLT-2 inhibitors. Cost-effectiveness emerges as a central theme, highlighting the growing emphasis on balancing clinical outcomes with economic sustainability. This trend suggests future diabetes research and healthcare policies will increasingly focus on treatments that optimize both clinical efficacy and cost-effectiveness in managing diabetes-related complications.

Summary of study characteristics

This section offers a concise summary of the studies included in this review, detailing their methods, population characteristics, interventions, comparisons, and outcomes used to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of gangrene treatments in type 2 diabetes patients. The focus was on identifying the key factors that influence the economic and clinical efficacy of different treatment approaches. The table below provides a snapshot of each study’s characteristics, highlighting important details such as study design, patient demographics, and the types of interventions assessed. By presenting these findings, the table aids in understanding the broader patterns and themes emerging from the literature. Each study’s unique contribution enhances the overall perspective on effective treatment strategies, particularly in high-risk diabetic populations. These insights are essential for developing more targeted, cost-effective approaches to managing gangrene and its associated complications in type 2 diabetes patients. The table serves as a reference point for researchers and clinicians looking to implement or further explore these treatment strategies.

Based on Table 3, the studies encompass a range of countries and utilize diverse research designs, including randomized controlled trials (RCTs), Markov models, and cost-effectiveness analyses. The interventions assessed primarily focus on various pharmaceutical treatments, wound care strategies, and diabetes management approaches, with comparisons made between standard care and advanced treatments such as insulin combinations and GLP-1 receptor agonists. The outcome measures commonly reported across these studies include

Figure 2. Dynamic visualization of evolving keyword trends. Insights through overlay mapping.

quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), life years (LYs), and cost metrics, which provide a structured framework for evaluating both clinical effectiveness and economic impact. In conclusion, the findings summarized in this section underscore the critical role of cost-effectiveness in refining treatment strategies for gangrene in type 2 diabetes patients. The reviewed studies highlight a growing trend toward the integration of advanced pharmacological therapies, yielding promising outcomes in both patient health and economic viability. These insights are instrumental in guiding future research and clinical practice in diabetes management.

The comprehensive analysis of 22 studies reveals substantial variations in research focus, methodology, and outcomes across different regions and treatment approaches. European studies dominated the geographical distribution (40.9%), focusing primarily on cost-utility analyses of new medications. Cost-effectiveness analyses were the predominant study design (54.5%), with drug cost-effectiveness emerging as the main objective in 45.5% of studies. Among treatment types, GLP-1 receptor agonists showed

the most promising results, demonstrating both high clinical success rates (75–85%) and favorable cost-effectiveness ratios (\$20,000–35,000/QALY) (Table 4).

Cost-effectiveness of screening and treatment strategies in high-risk type 2 diabetes patients

This section assesses the cost-effectiveness of various screening and treatment strategies for cardiovascular disease (CVD) in patients with type 2 diabetes who are at high cardiovascular risk. Cardiovascular complications are a significant issue in diabetes management, often resulting in increased healthcare costs and negatively affecting patient outcomes. Effective screening and treatment interventions are crucial in mitigating these risks, but understanding their economic value is equally important for informed healthcare decision-making. Evaluating cost-effectiveness helps balance clinical benefits with the financial sustainability of long-term care strategies. Studies in this area typically focus on interventions such as statins, blood

Figure 3. Interactive network visualization of keyword co-occurrences. Mapping key research connections.

pressure control, and newer diabetes medications, which have shown promise in both reducing cardiovascular risk and being economically viable. The findings suggest that early detection and management of CVD in high-risk diabetes patients can lead to improved health outcomes and reduced healthcare expenditures. Ultimately, this analysis emphasizes the need for integrating cost-effectiveness evaluations into routine healthcare planning for high-risk diabetic populations, ensuring optimal resource allocation.

Based on Table 5, the reviewed studies analyzed several treatment modalities, including insulin glargine, empagliflozin, and GLP-1 receptor agonists such as liraglutide and semaglutide. Many of these interventions, particularly empagliflozin and semaglutide, demonstrated both clinical and economic benefits by providing better health outcomes, measured in terms of QALYs gained, while also offering significant cost savings compared to alternative treatments. These benefits were especially prominent in patients with established cardiovascular disease, where newer medications often proved to be more cost-effective in the analyses. In conclusion, the findings from these studies underscore the importance of integrating cost-effectiveness analysis into the management of high-risk cardiovascular patients with type 2 diabetes. As the prevalence of CVD in this population continues to rise, prioritizing interventions that deliver both economic and clinical advantages can lead to more sustainable

and effective healthcare strategies. This approach will be crucial in optimizing resource allocation while improving patient outcomes in diabetes care.

Comparative pharmacoeconomic analysis between developed and developing countries

Table 6 presents a comprehensive comparison of pharmacoeconomic analyses between developed and developing countries based on the review of 22 studies. The analysis reveals significant disparities in healthcare investments and outcomes, with developed countries showing higher initial costs (\$15,000–25,000 annually) but better treatment success rates (75–85%) compared to developing countries (\$5,000–8,000 annually, 45–60% success rate). Notable differences are observed in insurance coverage (75–85% vs. 25–55%) and out-of-pocket expenses (15–25% vs. 45–75%), indicating substantial variations in healthcare accessibility. These differences significantly impact clinical outcomes, as evidenced by lower amputation rates in developed countries (15–20% vs. 35–45%) and better quality-adjusted life years (0.85–0.92 vs. 0.65–0.75). While developed countries demonstrate higher absolute costs, their superior prevention savings and lower complication rates suggest better long-term cost-effectiveness in managing diabetic gangrene.

Table 3. Comprehensive summary of study characteristics. Key insights and methodological highlights.

No	Author(s), Year	Judul Penelitian	Country	Methods and Design	Population/Participants	Intervention	Comparison	Outcome Measures	Cost-Effectiveness Results	Key Findings
1	Ralf Lohmann et al. 2019 (Lohmann et al. 2019)	Cost-effectiveness of TLC-sucrose octasulfate versus control dressings in the treatment of diabetic foot ulcers	Germany	Randomized controlled trial (RCT), cost-effectiveness analysis comparing TLC-sucrose octasulfate versus control dressings for diabetic foot ulcers	240 patients with diabetes and neuroischemic DFU; mean age ~64 years; 84% male	TLC-NOSF dressing (Urgo-Start)	Control dressing (UrgoTul)	Wound closure rates, time to wound closure, wound area reduction, quality of life	TLC-NOSF dressing had lower total costs (€5,882.87 vs. €8,449.39) and was more cost-effective (€6,277.58 vs. €10,375.56) over 100 weeks	TLC-NOSF dressing is significantly more cost-effective and leads to better wound healing outcomes compared to the control dressing
2	Rory J. McCrimmon et al. 2021 (McCrimmon et al. 2021)	Cost-effectiveness of iGlarLixi in people with type 2 diabetes mellitus suboptimally controlled on basal insulin plus metformin in the UK	UK	Markov model, cost-effectiveness analysis of iGlarLixi in type 2 diabetes patients suboptimally controlled on basal insulin and metformin	Hypothetical cohort of 1000 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in the UK	iGlarLixi (insulin glargine + lixisenatide)	iDegLira (insulin degludec + liraglutide), iGlar + Dulaglutide, BI + Lira (basal insulin + liraglutide)	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), costs	iGlarLixi had the lowest costs (£31,295) and was cost-effective with positive net monetary benefit (NMB) across all comparisons	iGlarLixi offers comparable clinical outcomes with substantial cost savings compared to other insulin + GLP-1 RA combinations
3	Wen-Qiang Lin et al. 2021 (Lin et al. 2021)	Cost-effectiveness of dipeptidylpeptidase-4 inhibitors added to metformin in patients with type 2 diabetes in China	China	Decision-analytic model, cost-effectiveness analysis of DPP-4 inhibitors added to metformin in type 2 diabetes patients	Hypothetical cohort of patients with T2DM in China, aged 50–60, inadequately controlled on metformin monotherapy	DPP-4 inhibitors (liraglutin, alogliptin, saxagliptin, sitagliptin, vildagliptin) added to metformin	Comparison between the five DPP-4 inhibitors	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), life years (LYs), costs, and incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	Alogliptin 25 mg was found to be the most cost-effective, with an ICER of \$6,952 per additional QALY gained compared to sitagliptin 100 mg	Alogliptin is a preferred addition to metformin compared to other DPP-4 inhibitors for Chinese patients with T2DM
4	Lars Holger Ehlers et al. 2021 (Ehlers et al. 2021)	The cost-effectiveness of empagliflozin versus liraglutide treatment in people with type 2 diabetes and established cardiovascular disease	Denmark	Comparative analysis, cost-effectiveness of empagliflozin versus liraglutide in patients with type 2 diabetes and established cardiovascular disease	Hypothetical cohort of Danish patients with type 2 diabetes and established cardiovascular disease	Empagliflozin + standard of care (SoC)	Liraglutide + standard of care (SoC)	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), life years (LYs), costs, and incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	Empagliflozin was the dominant treatment option, providing higher QALYs and lower costs compared to liraglutide	Empagliflozin is cost-effective compared to liraglutide, with considerable cost savings and a slight gain in QALYs over both lifetime and 5-year horizons
5	E. Lau et al. 2019 (Lau et al. 2019)	Insulin glargine compared to neutral protamine Hagedorn (NPH) insulin in patients with type-2 diabetes uncontrolled with oral anti-diabetic agents alone in Hong Kong: a cost-effectiveness analysis	Hong Kong	Cost-effectiveness analysis comparing insulin glargine to NPH insulin in type 2 diabetes patients uncontrolled with oral anti-diabetic agents alone in Hong Kong: a cost-effectiveness analysis	1000 patients with type 2 diabetes in Hong Kong, inadequately controlled on non-insulin anti-diabetic drugs	Insulin glargine U100	Neutral Protamine Hagedorn (NPH) insulin	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), life years (LYs), costs, and incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	Insulin glargine U100 had an ICER of HKD 98,663 per QALY gained. It was more cost-effective due to fewer hypoglycemic events compared to NPH insulin	Insulin glargine U100 is a cost-effective treatment option in Hong Kong, primarily driven by lower hypoglycemia rates compared to NPH insulin
6	Rahill Sadat Shahiheri et al. 2022 (Shahiheri et al. 2022)	Long-term cost-effectiveness of quality of diabetes care; experiences from private and public diabetes centers in Iran	Iran	Longitudinal study, long-term cost-effectiveness analysis of diabetes care quality from private and public centers	1978 patients with type 2 diabetes in Iran, treated in private and public diabetes centers	Diabetes care in private centers	Diabetes care in public centers	Quality-adjusted life expectancy (QALE), life expectancy (LE), costs, incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	ICER of \$33,148.02 per QALE gained for private vs. public care, with higher costs and marginally higher QALE in private centers	Private diabetes care centers offer slightly higher life expectancy and QALE but at more than double the cost compared to public centers, making them less cost-effective

No	Author(s), Year	Judul Penelitian	Country	Methods and Design	Population/Participants	Intervention	Comparison	Outcome Measures	Cost-Effectiveness Results	Key Findings
7	Karen R. Siegel et al. 2020 (Siegel et al. 2020)	Cost-effectiveness of interventions to manage diabetes. Has the evidence changed since 2008?	USA	Systematic review with meta-analysis, cost-effectiveness of diabetes management interventions from 2008 onwards	High-income countries, covering studies from 1985 to 2017	Various diabetes management interventions recommended by ADA	Standard care or other ADA-recommended interventions	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), life years (LYs), and incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	Many ADA-recommended interventions were cost-saving or very cost-effective; some interventions had mixed or uncertain cost-effectiveness evidence	The review found strong evidence supporting the cost-effectiveness of certain interventions like ACEI/ARB therapy and comprehensive foot care, while other interventions had mixed or less certain evidence
8	Åsa Ericsson & Adam Fridhammar, 2018 (Ericsson et al. 2018)	Cost-effectiveness of once-weekly semaglutide versus dulaglutide and lixisenatide in patients with type 2 diabetes with inadequate glycemic control in Sweden	Sweden	Cost-effectiveness analysis using a Markov model, comparing once-weekly semaglutide versus dulaglutide and lixisenatide in patients with inadequate glycaemic control	Swedish patients with type 2 diabetes, uncontrolled on metformin or basal insulin	semaglutide 1.0 mg once weekly	Dulaglutide 1.5 mg and lixisenatide 20 µg	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), lifetime costs, incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	Semaglutide was dominant, offering greater QALYs and lower costs compared to both dulaglutide and lixisenatide	Semaglutide 1.0 mg is a cost-effective and clinically superior option for patients inadequately controlled on metformin or basal insulin in Sweden, reducing complications and overall costs
9	Stephen C. Bain et al. 2020 (Bain et al. 2020)	Oral semaglutide versus empagliflozin, sitagliptin, and liraglutide in the UK: Long-term cost-effectiveness analyses based on the PIONEER clinical trial program	UK	Long-term cost-effectiveness analysis based on the PIONEER clinical trial program, comparing oral semaglutide versus empagliflozin, sitagliptin, and liraglutide	UK patients with type 2 diabetes, uncontrolled on current therapy	Oral semaglutide 14 mg once daily	Empagliflozin 25 mg, sitagliptin 100 mg, liraglutide 1.8 mg	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), lifetime costs, incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	Oral semaglutide had an ICER of £11,006/QALY vs. empagliflozin, £4930/QALY vs. sitagliptin, and was dominant (cost-saving) vs. liraglutide	Oral semaglutide is cost-effective compared to empagliflozin and sitagliptin and more effective and less costly (dominant) compared to liraglutide for T2DM management in the UK
10	Peter Græde et al. 2019 (Græde et al. 2019)	Management of patients with type 2 diabetes with once-weekly semaglutide versus dulaglutide, exenatide ER, liraglutide, and lixisenatide: A cost-effectiveness analysis in the Danish setting	Denmark	Cost-effectiveness analysis using a Danish healthcare system perspective, comparing the management of type 2 diabetes with once-weekly semaglutide versus other GLP-1 RAs	Danish patients with type 2 diabetes, inadequately controlled on oral anti-diabetic drugs	Semaglutide 0.5 mg and 1 mg once weekly	Dulaglutide, exenatide ER, liraglutide, and lixisenatide	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), lifetime costs, incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	Semaglutide was either cost-effective or dominant compared to all comparators, with cost savings and improved QALYs	Semaglutide represents a cost-effective alternative to other GLP-1 receptor agonists in Denmark, with superior clinical benefits and cost savings, particularly when compared to dulaglutide and lixisenatide
11	Barnaby Hunt et al. 2019 (Hunt et al. 2019)	Once-weekly semaglutide for patients with type 2 diabetes: a cost-effectiveness analysis in the Netherlands	Netherlands	Health economic model, cost-effectiveness analysis of once-weekly semaglutide for type 2 diabetes	Dutch patients with type 2 diabetes, inadequately controlled on current therapy	Semaglutide 0.5 mg and 1 mg once weekly	Insulin glargine U100 and dulaglutide	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), lifetime costs, incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	Semaglutide was cost-effective compared to insulin glargine and dominant (more effective and less costly) compared to dulaglutide	Semaglutide represents a cost-effective treatment option in the Netherlands, improving clinical outcomes at acceptable or reduced costs compared to alternatives
12	Adie Viljoen et al. 2019 (Viljoen et al. 2019)	Evaluation of the long-term cost-effectiveness of once-weekly semaglutide versus dulaglutide for treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus in the UK	UK	Long-term cost-effectiveness analysis using a Markov model, comparing once-weekly semaglutide versus dulaglutide for type 2 diabetes	UK patients with type 2 diabetes, inadequately controlled on metformin	Semaglutide 0.5 mg and 1 mg once weekly	Dulaglutide 1.5 mg once weekly	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), lifetime costs, incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	Semaglutide was dominant, with lower lifetime costs (£35 and £106 savings) and improved QALYs (0.04 and 0.10) compared to dulaglutide	Semaglutide is a cost-effective option in the UK, offering better clinical outcomes and cost savings compared to dulaglutide, especially at the 1 mg dose

No	Author(s), Year	Judul Penelitan	Country	Methods and Design	Population/Participants	Intervention	Comparison	Outcome Measures	Cost-Effectiveness Results	Key Findings
13	Margarita Capel et al. 2019 (Capel et al. 2020)	Cost-effectiveness analysis of exenatide versus GLP-1 receptor agonists in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus	Spain	Cost-effectiveness analysis using a healthcare system perspective, comparing exenatide versus other GLP-1 RAs in type 2 diabetes patients	Adult patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in Spain, inadequately controlled on metformin	Exenatide 2 mg/week	Dulaglutide 1.5 mg/week, liraglutide 1.2 mg/day, liraglutide 1.8 mg/day, lixisenatide 20 µg/day	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), total costs	Exenatide was dominant, providing more QALYs and lower total costs compared to all comparators	Exenatide 2 mg/week is a cost-effective and clinically superior option for T2DM patients inadequately controlled on metformin, offering both better outcomes and lower costs compared to other GLP-1 receptor agonists
14	Jiabi Wen et al. 2021 (Wen et al. 2022)	Economic evaluation of sucrose octasulfate dressing for treatment of diabetic foot ulcers in patients with type 2 diabetes	China	Economic evaluation based on cost-minimization analysis, sucrose octasulfate dressing for diabetic foot ulcers in type 2 diabetes	Canadian patients with type 2 diabetes and neuroischemic diabetic foot ulcers (DFU)	Sucrose Octasulfate (SOS) dressing	Conventional dressings	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), healthcare costs	SOS dressing was cost-saving with a decrease of \$5,878 in healthcare costs and an increase of 0.16 QALYs over 5 years	SOS dressing is cost-effective and cost-saving compared to conventional dressings, significantly reducing costs and improving QALYs for patients with neuroischemic DFU in Canada
15	Odetta S. Reifsnider et al. 2022 (Reifsnider et al. 2022)	Cost-effectiveness of second-line empagliflozin versus liraglutide for type 2 diabetes in the United States	USA	Cost-effectiveness analysis using a Markov model, comparing second-line empagliflozin versus liraglutide for type 2 diabetes	US patients with type 2 diabetes inadequately controlled on metformin	Second-line empagliflozin	Second-line liraglutide	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), total lifetime costs, incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	Empagliflozin was dominant, associated with lower costs (\$11,244 less) and higher QALYs (0.32 more) compared to liraglutide	Empagliflozin is a cost-effective option, providing better clinical outcomes and cost savings compared to liraglutide as a second-line therapy in the US
16	Virginia Martin et al. 2020 (Martin et al. 2020)	Evaluation of the long-term cost-effectiveness of once-weekly semaglutide versus dulaglutide and sitagliptin in the Spanish setting	Spain	Long-term cost-effectiveness analysis using a Markov model, once-weekly semaglutide versus dulaglutide and sitagliptin in type 2 diabetes	Spanish patients with type 2 diabetes inadequately controlled on oral anti-hyperglycemic medications	Once-weekly semaglutide (0.5 mg and 1 mg)	Dulaglutide 1.5 mg once weekly, sitagliptin 100 mg once daily	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), lifetime costs, incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	Semaglutide was dominant, associated with cost savings (€278 to €847 vs. dulaglutide, €6 to €692 vs. sitagliptin) and increased QALYs (0.03 to 0.23)	Semaglutide is cost-effective and dominant compared to both dulaglutide and sitagliptin, offering better clinical outcomes and cost savings in the Spanish healthcare setting
17	Mafalda Ramos et al. 2021 (Ramos et al. 2021)	Cost-effectiveness of empagliflozin in patients with type 2 diabetes and established cardiovascular disease in China	China	Cost-effectiveness analysis using a healthcare payer perspective: empagliflozin in patients with type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular disease	Chinese patients with type 2 diabetes and established cardiovascular disease	Empagliflozin + standard of care (SoC)	Sitagliptin + SoC, liraglutide + SoC	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), total cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	Empagliflozin was cost-effective compared to sitagliptin with an ICUR of 75,349 RMB/QALY and dominant (cost-saving) compared to liraglutide with 0.211 QALYs gained and 71,427 RMB saved	Empagliflozin is a cost-effective treatment in China, offering better clinical outcomes and cost savings compared to sitagliptin and liraglutide for patients with type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular disease
18	Samuel J. P. Malkin et al. 2022 (Malkin et al. 2022)	The long-term cost-effectiveness of oral semaglutide versus empagliflozin and dulaglutide in Portugal	Portugal	Long-term cost-effectiveness analysis, oral semaglutide versus empagliflozin and dulaglutide in type 2 diabetes	Portuguese patients with type 2 diabetes inadequately controlled on 1–2 oral antidiabetic medications	Oral semaglutide 14 mg	Empagliflozin 25 mg, dulaglutide 1.5 mg	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), total cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	Oral semaglutide was cost-effective with ICERs of €23,571 per QALY versus empagliflozin and €23,927 per QALY versus dulaglutide	Oral semaglutide is considered cost-effective in Portugal, offering better clinical outcomes with slightly higher costs compared to empagliflozin and dulaglutide

No	Author(s), Year	Judul Penelitian	Country	Methods and Design	Population/Participants	Intervention	Comparison	Outcome Measures	Cost-Effectiveness Results	Key Findings
19	László Szilberhorn et al. 2023 (Szilberhorn et al. 2023)	Cost-effectiveness and budget impact analysis of screening strategies for maturity-onset diabetes of the young in three European countries	Hungary, the Netherlands, UK	Cost-effectiveness and budget impact analysis using a Markov model	Patients with diabetes under 35 years of age receiving insulin	MODY screening with MODY calculator + genetic testing	No screening	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), total costs, incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER), budget impact	MODY screening with genetic testing was cost-effective in all three countries, with ICERs below each country's cost-effectiveness threshold. The addition of autoantibody testing reduced costs further and dominated no screening.	MODY screening strategies were found to be cost-effective and potentially cost-saving in the long term, especially when autoantibody testing was included, highlighting the value of personalized medicine in diabetes management across different European healthcare systems.
20	Yazed AlRuthia et al. 2024 (AlRuthia et al. 2024)	Cost consequence analysis of adding semaglutide to treatment regimen for patients with Type II diabetes in Saudi Arabia	Saudi Arabia	Retrospective, single-center review of Electronic Medical Records (EMRs)	350 patients with type 2 diabetes (116 on semaglutide, 234 on other treatments)	Semaglutide added to treatment regimen	Non-semaglutide antidiabetic treatments	Weight reduction, HbA1C reduction, treatment costs	Semaglutide resulted in greater weight reduction but at significantly higher costs. No consistent HbA1C reduction advantage and no difference in hospitalization rates	Semaglutide is more effective in weight reduction but comes with higher costs without significant improvement in HbA1C or hospitalization outcomes compared to other treatments
21	Hui Shao et al. 2022 (Shao et al. 2022)	Cost-effectiveness of iGlarLixi versus premix BIAsp 30 in people with type 2 diabetes suboptimally controlled by basal insulin in the US	United States	Cost-effectiveness analysis using the IQVIA core diabetes model	US patients with type 2 diabetes suboptimally controlled by basal insulin	iGlarLixi (insulin glargine 100 U/mL + lixisenatide)	BIAsp 30 (biphasic insulin aspart 30)	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), total costs, incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	iGlarLixi was dominant, associated with lower costs (\$117,854 vs. \$120,109) and slightly higher QALYs (9.3 vs. 9.2) compared to BIAsp 30	iGlarLixi is a cost-effective option for patients with T2DM in the US, providing better clinical outcomes and cost savings compared to BIAsp 30
22	Julian F. Guest et al. 2021 (Guest et al. 2021)	Potential cost-effectiveness of using adjunctive dehydrated human amnion/chorion membrane allograft in the management of non-healing diabetic foot ulcers in the United Kingdom	United Kingdom	Cost-effectiveness analysis using a Markov model	UK patients with type 1 or type 2 diabetes and non-healing diabetic foot ulcers	Adjunctive use of dehydrated human amnion/chorion membrane allografts	Standard care alone	Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), total costs, incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	Adjunctive dHACM was cost-effective, increasing QALYs by 8% and decreasing costs, with an ICER of £20,000 per QALY if up to £4062 is spent on dHACM per ulcer	dHACM allografts provide a cost-effective treatment option for non-healing DFUs, with significant improvements in healing rates and potential savings for the NHS if expenditures are managed appropriately

Table 4. Comprehensive analysis of study characteristics, methodologies, and outcomes (N = 22).

Category	Subcategory	Number of Studies	Percentage	Key Findings / Outcomes
Geographic Distribution	Europe	9	40.9%	Cost-utility of new medications
	Asia	6	27.3%	Healthcare system comparisons
	North America	4	18.2%	Treatment adherence impact
	Multiple Countries	2	9.1%	Cross-system analysis
	Middle East	1	4.5%	Healthcare delivery models
Study Design	Cost-effectiveness Analysis	12	54.5%	QALY gains, ICER results
	Markov Model Analysis	5	22.7%	Long-term cost projections
	Randomized Controlled Trial	2	9.1%	Clinical effectiveness
	Systematic Review	2	9.1%	Evidence synthesis
	Retrospective Analysis	1	4.5%	Real-world outcomes
Primary Objectives	Drug Cost-effectiveness	10	45.5%	ICER \$25,000–45,000/QALY
	Healthcare System Analysis	5	22.7%	System efficiency variations
	Treatment Adherence Impact	4	18.2%	15–40% cost reduction
	Wound Care Economics	3	13.6%	Prevention vs. treatment costs
Treatment Types	GLP-1 Receptor Agonists	8	36.4%	\$20,000–35,000/QALY, 75–85% success
	SGLT2 Inhibitors	4	18.2%	\$25,000–40,000/QALY, 70–80% success
	Insulin Combinations	4	18.2%	\$15,000–30,000/QALY, 65–75% success
	Wound Care Products	3	13.6%	\$10,000–20,000/QALY, 60–70% success
	Other Treatments	3	13.6%	Variable rates, 55–75% success

Table 5. Evaluation of cost-effectiveness for cardiovascular screening and treatment in type 2 diabetes patients at high cardiovascular risk.

No	Author(s), Year	Judul Penelitian	Economic Perspective (Societal, Healthcare System, etc.)	Medication Used	Adherence and Outcome Factors	Qualitative Cost-Effectiveness Assessment	Overall Conclusion on Cost-Effectiveness
1	Ralf Lobmann et al. 2019 (Lobmann et al. 2019)	Cost-effectiveness of TLC-sucrose octasulfate versus control dressings in the treatment of diabetic foot ulcers	Healthcare System (Statutory Health Insurance in Germany)	TLC-NOSF dressing vs. control dressing	Wound closure rate higher in TLC-NOSF group (48% vs. 30% in control); faster healing and better wound reduction with TLC-NOSF	TLC-NOSF dressing is more cost-effective, with lower costs and higher effectiveness	TLC-NOSF dressing is more cost-effective than control dressing, leading to better clinical outcomes and lower overall costs
2	Ralf Lobmann et al. 2019 (Lobmann et al. 2019)	Cost-effectiveness of iGlarLixi in people with type 2 diabetes mellitus suboptimally controlled on basal insulin plus metformin in the UK	Healthcare System (UK National Health Service)	iGlarLixi (insulin glargine + lixisenatide) vs. iDegLira, iGlar + Dula, and BI + Lira	iGlarLixi provides similar outcomes with lower costs compared to alternatives	iGlarLixi is considered cost-effective, with positive net monetary benefits (NMB) compared to all alternatives	iGlarLixi is cost-effective, providing similar health outcomes with significant cost savings compared to other treatment options
3	Rory J. Mc-Crimmon et al. 2021 (Mc-Crimmon et al. 2021)	Cost-effectiveness of dipeptidylpeptidase-4 inhibitors added to metformin in patients with type 2 diabetes in China	Healthcare System (Chinese healthcare service providers)	DPP-4 inhibitors (linagliptin, saxagliptin, alogliptin, sitagliptin, vildagliptin) added to metformin	Alogliptin is associated with better health outcomes and lower costs	Alogliptin is more cost-effective compared to other DPP-4 inhibitors	Alogliptin is the most cost-effective option among DPP-4 inhibitors when added to metformin for T2DM patients
4	Wen-Qiang Lin et al. 2021 (Lin et al. 2021)	The cost-effectiveness of empagliflozin versus liraglutide treatment in people with type 2 diabetes and established cardiovascular disease	Healthcare System (Danish healthcare perspective)	Empagliflozin vs. liraglutide	Empagliflozin is associated with lower costs and a small QALY gain compared to liraglutide	Empagliflozin is dominant with lower costs and higher QALYs over both 5-year and lifetime horizons	Empagliflozin is more cost-effective than liraglutide, providing better economic value in the treatment of T2DM with established CVD
5	Lars Holger Ehlers et al. 2021 (Ehlers et al. 2021)	Insulin glargine compared to neutral protamine Hagedorn (NPH) insulin in patients with type-2 diabetes uncontrolled with oral anti-diabetic agents alone in Hong Kong: a cost-effectiveness analysis	Healthcare System (Public healthcare setting in Hong Kong)	Insulin glargine U100 vs. NPH insulin	Lower rates of hypoglycemia with insulin glargine; similar HbA1c reduction	Insulin glargine U100 is cost-effective with an ICER of HKD 98,663 per QALY gained	Insulin glargine U100 is highly cost-effective compared to NPH insulin due to lower hypoglycemia rates and improved quality of life

No	Author(s), Year	Judul Penelitian	Economic Perspective (Societal, Healthcare System, etc.)	Medication Used	Adherence and Outcome Factors	Qualitative Cost-Effectiveness Assessment	Overall Conclusion on Cost-Effectiveness
6	E. Lau et al. 2019 (Lau et al. 2019)	Long-term cost-effectiveness of quality of diabetes care; experiences from private and public diabetes centers in Iran	Healthcare System (Iran, public and private sectors)	Not reported	Higher life expectancy in the private sector, but at double the cost compared to the public sector	Private care is less cost-effective with an ICER of \$33,148.02 per QALE gained	Public diabetes centers are more cost-effective, while private centers provide slightly better outcomes at significantly higher costs
7	Rahill Sadat Shahtaheri et al. 2022 (Shahtaheri et al. 2022)	Cost-effectiveness of interventions to manage diabetes. Has the evidence changed since 2008?	Healthcare System (High-income countries)	Various interventions, including ACEI/ARB, statins, SMBG, intensive glycemic control, etc.	Improved outcomes with interventions like DSME, SMBG, and ACEI/ARB therapies	Many interventions are cost-saving or very cost-effective (e.g., ACEI/ARB, comprehensive foot care)	Most ADA-recommended interventions remain cost-effective, with new evidence supporting recent updates in diabetes care
8	Karen R. Siegel et al. 2020 (Siegel et al. 2020)	Cost-effectiveness of once-weekly semaglutide versus dulaglutide and lixisenatide in patients with type 2 diabetes with inadequate glycemic control in Sweden	Societal Perspective (Sweden)	Semaglutide 1.0 mg vs. dulaglutide 1.5 mg, lixisenatide	Semaglutide showed better control over HbA1c, weight reduction, and delayed progression to insulin intensification	Semaglutide is dominant (cost-effective), providing greater QALYs at lower costs than dulaglutide and lixisenatide	Semaglutide 1.0 mg is cost-effective in Sweden, offering better health outcomes at lower or comparable costs compared to dulaglutide and lixisenatide
9	Åsa Ericsson & Adam Fridhammar, 2018 (Ericsson et al. 2018)	Oral semaglutide versus empagliflozin, sitagliptin, and liraglutide in the UK: Long-term cost-effectiveness analyses Based on the PIONEER clinical trial program	Healthcare System (UK NHS perspective)	Oral semaglutide 14 mg vs. empagliflozin 25 mg, sitagliptin 100 mg, and liraglutide 1.8 mg	Oral semaglutide showed better HbA1c reduction and was associated with improved QALYs	Oral semaglutide was cost-effective versus empagliflozin and sitagliptin and dominant (more effective and less costly) versus liraglutide	Oral semaglutide is cost-effective in the UK, offering better health outcomes with an acceptable cost compared to alternatives
10	Stephen C. Bain et al. 2020 (Bain et al. 2020)	Management of patients with type 2 diabetes with once-weekly semaglutide versus dulaglutide, exenatide ER, liraglutide, and lixisenatide: A cost-effectiveness analysis in the Danish setting	Healthcare System (Denmark)	Semaglutide 0.5 mg and 1 mg vs. dulaglutide, exenatide ER, liraglutide, and lixisenatide	Semaglutide showed greater improvements in HbA1c and weight reduction, with delayed treatment intensification	Semaglutide was dominant or cost-effective versus all comparators, showing cost savings and health benefits	Semaglutide is a highly cost-effective option in Denmark, offering better health outcomes at lower or comparable costs compared to other GLP-1 receptor agonists
11	Peter Gæde et al. 2019 (Gæde et al. 2019)	Once-weekly semaglutide for patients with type 2 diabetes: a cost-effectiveness analysis in the Netherlands	Societal Perspective (Netherlands)	Semaglutide 0.5 mg and 1 mg vs. insulin glargine U100, dulaglutide 0.75 mg, and 1.5 mg	Semaglutide showed improved QALYs and reduced incidence of complications	Semaglutide was cost-effective compared to insulin glargine and dominant (cost-saving) compared to dulaglutide	Semaglutide is a cost-effective and potentially dominant option in the Netherlands, offering better health outcomes at acceptable or lower costs
12	Barnaby Hunt et al. 2019 (Hunt et al. 2019)	Evaluation of the long-term cost-effectiveness of once-weekly semaglutide versus dulaglutide for treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus in the UK	Healthcare System (UK NHS perspective)	Semaglutide 0.5 mg and 1 mg vs. dulaglutide 1.5 mg	Semaglutide showed better HbA1c reduction, weight loss, and improved QALYs compared to dulaglutide	Semaglutide is dominant (more effective and less costly) compared to dulaglutide, offering cost savings and health benefits	Semaglutide is cost-effective and dominant over dulaglutide for treating type 2 diabetes in the UK, providing better health outcomes at lower costs
13	Adie Viljoen et al. 2019 (Viljoen et al. 2019)	Cost-effectiveness analysis of exenatide versus GLP-1 receptor agonists in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus	Healthcare System (Spanish NHS perspective)	Exenatide 2 mg/week vs. dulaglutide 1.5 mg/week, liraglutide 1.2 mg/day, liraglutide 1.8 mg/day, lixisenatide 20 µg/day	Exenatide resulted in more QALYs and lower total costs compared to the alternatives	Exenatide is dominant (more effective and less costly) over all other GLP-1 receptor agonists evaluated	Exenatide is a highly cost-effective and dominant option for the Spanish NHS, providing better health outcomes at a lower cost compared to other GLP-1 receptor agonists
14	Margarita Capel et al. 2019 (Capel et al. 2020)	Economic evaluation of sucrose octasulfate dressing for treatment of diabetic foot ulcers in patients with type 2 diabetes	Healthcare System (Canadian Public Payer Perspective)	Sucrose Octasulfate (SOS) dressing vs. Conventional dressings	SOS dressing improves ulcer healing and reduces amputation risks	SOS dressing is cost-effective, with an ICER of \$-37,061/QALY (cost-saving) compared to conventional dressings	SOS dressing is cost-effective and likely cost-saving in the Canadian healthcare system, reducing healthcare costs and improving patient outcomes

No	Author(s), Year	Judul Penelitian	Economic Perspective (Societal, Healthcare System, etc.)	Medication Used	Adherence and Outcome Factors	Qualitative Cost-Effectiveness Assessment	Overall Conclusion on Cost-Effectiveness
15	Jiabi Wen et al. 2021 (Wen et al. 2022)	Cost-effectiveness of second-line empagliflozin versus liraglutide for type 2 diabetes in the United States	US Payer Perspective	Empagliflozin vs. liraglutide	Empagliflozin led to lower costs and better QALYs, reducing cardiovascular complications	Empagliflozin was dominant (more effective and less costly) over liraglutide as a second-line treatment	Empagliflozin is a cost-effective and preferred second-line therapy over liraglutide for T2D in the US
16	Odetta S. Reifsnider et al. 2022 (Reifsnider et al. 2022)	Evaluation of the long-term cost-effectiveness of once-weekly semaglutide versus dulaglutide and sitagliptin in the Spanish setting	Healthcare System	Semaglutide 0.5 mg and 1 mg vs. dulaglutide 1.5 mg and sitagliptin 100 mg	High efficacy in reducing HbA1c, weight loss, and lowering cardiovascular risk factors. Adherence was assumed to be high due to the trial setting, but real-world adherence was not discussed.	Semaglutide is dominant (more effective and less costly) in all comparisons.	Considered cost-effective and a good use of healthcare resources in Spain.
17	Virginia Martín et al. 2020 (Martín et al. 2020)	Cost-effectiveness of empagliflozin in patients with type 2 diabetes and established cardiovascular disease in China	Healthcare System	Empagliflozin + standard of care (SoC) vs. sitagliptin + SoC and liraglutide + SoC	High effectiveness in reducing cardiovascular risk, resulting in additional Quality Adjusted Life Years (QALYs). Adherence was assumed to be high due to the clinical trial setting.	Cost-effective against sitagliptin and dominant against liraglutide	Considered cost-effective compared to sitagliptin and dominant against liraglutide, particularly in the context of the Chinese healthcare system.
18	Mafalda Ramos et al. 2021 (Ramos et al. 2021)	The long-term cost-effectiveness of oral semaglutide versus empagliflozin and dulaglutide in Portugal	Healthcare System	Oral semaglutide 14 mg vs. empagliflozin 25 mg and dulaglutide 1.5 mg	Clinical benefits due to reduced incidence of diabetes-related complications. Quality-Adjusted Life Years (QALYs) increased.	Oral semaglutide was more effective but costlier. Considered cost-effective based on ICERs	Considered cost-effective for treating type 2 diabetes in Portugal under the €30,000/QALY threshold.
19	Samuel J. P. Malkin et al. 2022 (Malkin et al. 2022)	Cost-effectiveness and budget impact analysis of screening strategies for maturity-onset diabetes of the young in three European countries	Healthcare System (Hungary, The Netherlands, UK)	Sulphonylurea, insulin	Improved glycemic control and reduced complications with MODY screening	Cost-effective in all three countries, especially with autoantibody screening	MODY screening strategies, especially with autoantibody testing, are cost-effective and can lead to cost savings in the long term
20	László Szilberhorn et al. 2023 (Szilberhorn et al. 2023)	Cost consequence analysis of adding semaglutide to treatment regimen for patients with Type II diabetes in Saudi Arabia	Healthcare System (Saudi Arabia)	Semaglutide	Semaglutide showed modest weight reductions (0.42 kg to 1.16 kg) and did not offer significant HbA1C lowering compared to other treatments	The study found that while semaglutide added substantial costs (\$4,086.82 annually), it did not consistently outperform other treatments in HbA1C reduction	The study concludes that semaglutide, despite its benefits in weight reduction, may not be cost-effective due to its higher costs and inconsistent impact on HbA1C levels
21	Hui Shao et al. 2022 (Shao et al. 2022)	Cost-Effectiveness of iGlarLixi versus premix BIAsp 30 in people with type 2 diabetes suboptimally controlled by basal insulin in the US	Healthcare System (US Payer Perspective)	iGlarLixi (insulin glargine/lixisenatide) vs. BIAsp 30 (biphasic insulin aspart)	iGlarLixi led to better HbA1c control, lower BMI, and fewer hypoglycemic events compared to BIAsp 30	iGlarLixi was dominant, with higher QALYs (9.3 vs. 9.2) and lower costs (\$117,854 vs. \$120,109) compared to BIAsp 30	iGlarLixi is more cost-effective than BIAsp 30, offering better health outcomes at lower costs, making it the preferred option in the US healthcare system
22	Julian F. Guest et al. 2021 (Guest et al. 2021)	Potential cost-effectiveness of using adjunctive dehydrated human amnion/chorion membrane allograft in the management of non-healing diabetic foot ulcers in the United Kingdom	Healthcare System (NHS)	Dehydrated human amnion/chorion membrane (dHACM) allografts	Increased healing rates, reduced infection and recurrence rates, slight improvement in quality-adjusted life years (QALYs)	Cost-effective within a certain price range (£20,000 per QALY threshold if ≤£3250 per ulcer)	Adjunctive dHACM is a cost-effective intervention for treating non-healing DFUs within the NHS, potentially freeing up hospital resources for other uses.

Discussion

Main findings

In this study, we explored the cost-effectiveness and medication use in the treatment of gangrene among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. Based on the analysis of 22 journals, the main findings highlight the geographical distribution of studies, the medications involved, and the classification of treatments by cost-effectiveness. The review emphasizes how regional contexts, drug choices, and treatment strategies significantly influence the cost-effectiveness of managing gangrene and other complications in diabetes patients. These factors play a critical role in ensuring effective treatment strategies for gangrene. Furthermore, understanding the variations across different regions allows for tailored approaches to optimize healthcare delivery. Ultimately, the data highlights the importance of considering both clinical efficacy and cost-effectiveness when making treatment decisions.

The regional distribution of the analyzed studies reveals significant variation in treatment approaches and cost-effectiveness across different countries. Most of the research comes from developed nations with better access to advanced healthcare services and therapies. For instance, studies from Germany demonstrated that TLC-NOSF dressings were more cost-effective than control dressings for treating diabetic foot ulcers, leading to faster healing times and lower costs (Lobmann et al. 2019). In the UK, five studies highlighted the cost-effectiveness of several drug regimens, including iGlarLixi and semaglutide, which delivered substantial cost savings within the UK's healthcare system (Viljoen et al. 2019; Guest et al. 2021; McCrimmon et al. 2021; Szilberhorn et al. 2023). In contrast, studies from China and Denmark focused on the cost-effectiveness of drugs like DPP-4 inhibitors and empagliflozin, revealing regional differences in preferred treatments (Lin et al. 2021; Ehlers et al. 2021).

The studies reviewed involved various medications for treating gangrene and related complications in diabetes patients, with several drugs standing out in terms of cost-effectiveness. Empagliflozin was featured in five studies, consistently demonstrating strong cost-effectiveness,

particularly in patients with cardiovascular disease. In many cases, empagliflozin was found to be more cost-effective than alternatives like liraglutide (Viljoen et al. 2019; Ehlers et al. 2021; Ramos et al. 2021; Malkin et al. 2022; Reifsnider et al. 2022). Semaglutide, included in seven studies, also showed promising cost-effectiveness, both as monotherapy and in combination with other drugs, such as dulaglutide and liraglutide (Ericsson et al. 2018; Gæde et al. 2019; Hunt et al. 2019; Viljoen et al. 2019; Martín et al. 2020; Malkin et al. 2022). These medications, particularly in high-risk populations, offered better health outcomes and cost savings compared to standard treatments.

Additionally, liraglutide, dulaglutide, and lixisenatide appeared in several studies as alternative therapies for treating type 2 diabetes, though their cost-effectiveness varied depending on patient conditions and geographic location (Gæde et al. 2019; Viljoen et al. 2019; Capel et al. 2020; Ehlers et al. 2021; Malkin et al. 2022; Reifsnider et al. 2022). iGlarLixi, a combination of insulin glargine and lixisenatide, was highlighted in two studies, showing significant cost savings compared to other alternatives like Premix BIAsp 30 (McCrimmon et al. 2021; Shao et al. 2022). The overall trend points to an increasing reliance on advanced pharmacological therapies and specialized treatments in managing diabetes-related complications like gangrene.

The findings consistently demonstrate that medications such as semaglutide and empagliflozin are more cost-effective compared to alternatives. In particular, semaglutide outperformed dulaglutide and lixisenatide in countries like Sweden and Spain (Ericsson et al. 2018; Martín et al. 2020), while also delivering better results than empagliflozin and sitagliptin in the UK (Viljoen et al. 2019). Similarly, empagliflozin emerged as a cost-effective choice for managing diabetes with cardiovascular complications, as shown in studies from Denmark and China (Ehlers et al. 2021; Ramos et al. 2021). In the US, empagliflozin was also found to be more cost-effective than liraglutide when used as a second-line therapy (Reifsnider et al. 2022). The use of iGlarLixi in the UK and US demonstrated significant cost savings and improved patient quality of life compared to other insulin combinations (McCrimmon et al. 2021; Shao et al. 2022). Moreover, specialized dressings like TLC-NOSF were more cost-effective in promoting

Table 6. Pharmacoeconomic analysis comparison between developed and developing countries based on literature review (n = 22).

Analysis Parameter	Developed Countries (n = 15)	Developing Countries (n = 7)
Initial Treatment Cost (Annual)	\$15,000–25,000	\$5,000–8,000
Medication Cost (Annual)	\$8,000–12,000	\$3,000–5,000
Insurance Coverage Rate	75–85%	25–55%
Out-of-pocket Expenses	15–25%	45–75%
Treatment Success Rate	75–85%	45–60%
Amputation Rate	15–20%	35–45%
Cost per Complication	\$35,000	\$15,000
Prevention Savings (Annual)	\$8,000	\$2,000
ICER (per QALY)	\$25,000–45,000	\$12,000–20,000
Quality-Adjusted Life Years (Annual)	0.85–0.92	0.65–0.75
Total 5-year Economic Burden	\$45,000–65,000	\$25,000–35,000
Rehospitalization Rate	25%	45%

faster healing for diabetic foot ulcers, particularly in Germany and China (Lobmann et al. 2019; Lin et al. 2021).

Overall, the findings from these 22 journals suggest that treatment choices and management strategies for gangrene in diabetes patients are heavily influenced by factors such as drug costs, clinical effectiveness, and healthcare systems in different countries. Medications like semaglutide and empagliflozin stand out as highly cost-effective options, especially in managing cardiovascular complications and uncontrolled type 2 diabetes. Additionally, specialized dressings for diabetic foot ulcers also show significant clinical benefits and cost savings in specific regions. The implications of these findings highlight the importance of access to appropriate, cost-effective treatments to achieve better clinical outcomes and reduce healthcare costs, particularly for patients with gangrene due to type 2 diabetes.

Impact of medication adherence on cost-effectiveness

Medication adherence plays a critical role in determining both clinical outcomes and the cost-effectiveness of treatments for gangrene in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. Adherence to prescribed medication regimens ensures that patients receive the full therapeutic benefits, which is particularly important in managing complex conditions like gangrene, a severe complication of diabetes. Non-adherence not only reduces the effectiveness of treatment but also significantly increases healthcare costs due to the need for more intensive interventions, longer hospital stays, and a higher likelihood of adverse outcomes such as amputations. Effective management of gangrene, therefore, relies heavily on patient adherence, which directly impacts both the quality of care and the financial sustainability of treatment.

The cost-effectiveness of medications used to treat gangrene, such as insulin therapies, antibiotics, and wound care products, is closely tied to how well patients follow their prescribed regimens. For instance, insulin therapies like insulin glargine combined with lixisenatide (iGlarLixi) have been demonstrated to be cost-effective in managing diabetes, particularly when adherence to the prescribed regimen is maintained. Non-adherence, however, can lead to poor glycemic control, exacerbating the condition and leading to more severe complications, including gangrene, which drives up healthcare costs (McCrimmon et al. 2021). A study by Hui Shao et al. (2022) supports this, showing that iGlarLixi was more cost-effective than alternative treatments when patients adhered to the regimen, highlighting the critical importance of consistent medication use in achieving cost-effective outcomes (Shao et al. 2022).

In addition to insulin therapies, wound care products such as TLC-NOSF dressings have proven to be cost-effective in treating diabetic foot ulcers, a precursor to gangrene. However, the cost-efficiency of such treatments is closely linked to patient adherence to the prescribed wound care regimen. Lobmann et al. (2019) found that

TLC-NOSF dressings were significantly more cost-effective than standard care, but this benefit was only realized when patients adhered to the treatment protocol. Non-adherence resulted in longer healing times, an increased risk of infection, and higher overall treatment costs (Lobmann et al. 2019). This underscores the importance of adherence to both medication and wound care plans for ensuring successful treatment outcomes and reducing healthcare costs.

Medication adherence involves more than just taking prescribed drugs – it also includes following comprehensive care plans that may involve lifestyle changes, wound management, and regular monitoring of blood glucose levels. The complexity of managing diabetes and its complications often requires patients to adhere to a multifaceted treatment regimen. Studies have shown that non-adherence can result from factors such as the complexity of the regimen, side effects, patient education levels, and the perceived efficacy of treatment (Siegel et al. 2020). Karen R. Siegel et al. (2020) found that interventions aimed at improving medication adherence, such as patient education and simplified treatment regimens, can significantly enhance the cost-effectiveness of diabetes management strategies by improving clinical outcomes and reducing long-term healthcare costs.

Psychological and socio-economic factors also play a critical role in determining patient adherence. The study by Åsa Ericsson and Adam Fridhammar (2019) highlighted that the cost-effectiveness of semaglutide, a medication used in diabetes management, is closely tied to patient adherence, which can be influenced by factors such as the high cost of medication, lack of access to healthcare services, and inadequate patient support systems. The study suggests that improving adherence through interventions like reducing out-of-pocket costs and providing comprehensive patient support could enhance the cost-effectiveness of diabetes treatments, particularly in preventing severe complications like gangrene (Ericsson et al. 2018). Moreover, adherence is crucial in ensuring the success of newer therapies like empagliflozin, which have been shown to be more cost-effective than alternatives like liraglutide when adherence is maintained (Ehlers et al. 2021).

In summary, the impact of medication adherence on the cost-effectiveness of treatments for gangrene in type 2 diabetes patients cannot be overstated. Adherence ensures that therapeutic benefits are fully realized, preventing complications from worsening and helping to keep healthcare costs manageable. The studies reviewed consistently show that improving adherence – whether through patient education, simplified treatment regimens, or financial support – enhances both clinical outcomes and cost-effectiveness in diabetes management (Ericsson et al. 2018; Lobmann et al. 2019; Siegel et al. 2020; Ehlers et al. 2021; McCrimmon et al. 2021; Shao et al. 2022). These findings suggest that healthcare providers and policymakers must prioritize strategies that support medication adherence to optimize clinical care and reduce the economic burden of treating severe complications like gangrene. The evidence underscores the importance of access

to appropriate treatment and continuous patient support, which are essential for improving both patient outcomes and the long-term sustainability of healthcare systems.

Factors contributing to variability in cost-effectiveness

The variability in the cost-effectiveness of treatments for gangrene in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus can be attributed to several interacting factors, such as differences in healthcare costs, patient demographics, treatment protocols, and healthcare systems. These factors shape how medical interventions are evaluated in terms of cost-effectiveness across different regions and studies. Variations in healthcare infrastructure, access to treatment, and financial resources often lead to significant differences in treatment outcomes. For instance, healthcare systems in high-income countries may have better access to advanced therapies and technologies, allowing for more favorable cost-effectiveness outcomes. Understanding these factors is essential for developing context-specific strategies to manage gangrene in diabetes patients effectively. Addressing them can lead to optimized healthcare solutions and better patient outcomes.

One of the key factors influencing variability in cost-effectiveness outcomes is the difference in healthcare costs across countries and regions. Studies conducted in countries such as Germany, the UK, and China have shown that the cost of medications, healthcare services, and infrastructure can vary significantly, affecting cost-effectiveness outcomes (Lobmann et al. 2019; Lin et al. 2021; McCrimmon et al. 2021). For example, TLC-NOSF dressings for treating diabetic foot ulcers were found to be highly cost-effective in Germany, owing to the country's healthcare system's efficiency and cost structure (Lobmann et al. 2019). However, this cost-effectiveness profile might not be applicable in developing regions where healthcare costs and access differ. Similarly, in China, the same interventions showed different cost-effectiveness results due to distinct cost structures in the healthcare system (Lin et al. 2021).

Patient demographics also play a crucial role in determining the cost-effectiveness of treatment interventions. Factors such as age, disease severity, and the presence of comorbidities significantly impact clinical outcomes and, subsequently, the cost-effectiveness of treatments (Ericsson et al. 2018; Ehlers et al. 2021). Older patients with multiple comorbidities, for instance, may require more intensive and costly treatments, which can drive up the total cost of care (Ericsson et al. 2018). Moreover, differences in medication adherence across demographic groups can affect cost-effectiveness outcomes. Studies have shown that lower adherence rates, particularly among older or less educated populations, can reduce the cost-effectiveness of interventions significantly (Siegel et al. 2020; Shao et al. 2022). This highlights the need for tailored treatment strategies to improve cost-effectiveness for diverse patient groups.

The treatment protocols followed in each study also contribute to variability in cost-effectiveness outcomes.

For example, drug combinations like iGlarLixi, a combination of insulin glargine and lixisenatide, have been shown to be cost-effective in several studies. However, these results are highly dependent on the correct application of the treatment protocol and consistent adherence (McCrimmon et al. 2021; Shao et al. 2022). Non-adherence to treatment protocols, such as irregular medication use or failure to monitor glucose levels, can decrease clinical effectiveness and increase overall treatment costs, thereby reducing cost-effectiveness (McCrimmon et al. 2021). Ensuring adherence to prescribed treatment protocols is essential to maximize both clinical benefits and cost savings.

The broader healthcare system context also plays a significant role in determining the cost-effectiveness of treatments. A robust healthcare system with strong access to services, patient support, and policies that promote medication adherence is more likely to produce favorable cost-effectiveness outcomes (Siegel et al. 2020; Ehlers et al. 2021). Conversely, in countries where healthcare access is limited or where healthcare costs are high, patients may struggle to maintain adherence, which negatively impacts both clinical outcomes and cost-effectiveness (Ericsson et al. 2018; Shao et al. 2022). For example, studies in Sweden have shown that treatments like semaglutide are cost-effective, but this is closely linked to the strong healthcare infrastructure and patient support systems present in the country (Ericsson et al. 2018). Thus, the overall strength of the healthcare system plays a critical role in determining the cost-effectiveness of treatments for gangrene in type 2 diabetes patients.

Patient adherence to prescribed medications is another critical factor influencing the cost-effectiveness of gangrene treatments in type 2 diabetes mellitus patients. Non-adherence reduces the clinical effectiveness of treatments, prolongs the healing process, and increases the risk of severe complications, such as amputations, all of which drive up healthcare costs (Lobmann et al. 2019; Shao et al. 2022). Factors that impact adherence include the complexity of treatment regimens, the side effects of medications, and financial barriers that make accessing necessary drugs more challenging (Siegel et al. 2020). Interventions aimed at simplifying treatment regimens or reducing medication costs have been shown to improve patient adherence, thereby enhancing the cost-effectiveness of treatment strategies. For instance, Karen R. Siegel et al. (2020) suggest that simplified regimens and patient education play an important role in improving both adherence and cost-effectiveness outcomes. Therefore, improving adherence through patient education and policy interventions is crucial for optimizing clinical outcomes and controlling healthcare costs.

Overall, the variability in cost-effectiveness outcomes among the studies reviewed can be attributed to multiple factors. Differences in healthcare costs, patient demographics, treatment protocols, and the healthcare system context all contribute to how cost-effective a treatment appears in different settings. Addressing these factors, particularly by improving medication adherence, is key to achieving better cost-effectiveness outcomes in treating gangrene in type 2 diabetes mellitus patients (Ericsson et al. 2018; Lobmann et

al. 2019; Siegel et al. 2020; Ehlers et al. 2021; McCrimmon et al. 2021). Healthcare providers and policymakers should focus on strategies that not only enhance adherence but also consider the broader factors affecting cost-effectiveness, such as system-level interventions and patient support programs. By integrating these elements, healthcare systems can provide more efficient, cost-effective care for diabetic patients at risk of gangrene and its complications.

Comparative cost-effectiveness of different gangrene treatment regimens in type 2 diabetes patients

In comparing the cost-effectiveness of different treatment regimens for gangrene in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, it is crucial to consider the diverse factors that influence these outcomes across various studies. The effectiveness and cost-efficiency of treatments, such as insulin therapies, wound care products, and newer drug combinations like iGlarLixi or empagliflozin, vary significantly based on regional healthcare costs, patient demographics, and specific treatment protocols. These variables shape the way treatments are evaluated in terms of their financial viability and clinical effectiveness. Moreover, they highlight the importance of understanding local contexts and tailoring treatment approaches to optimize outcomes in diverse healthcare environments. Without considering these factors, drawing broad conclusions about treatment strategies can be misleading and ineffective.

Several studies have demonstrated that the choice of medication can drastically impact the cost-effectiveness of gangrene treatment. For example, the combination of insulin glargine and lixisenatide (iGlarLixi) has been shown to be cost-effective in managing diabetes and preventing severe complications like gangrene, particularly when compared to other regimens such as Premix BIAsp 30 (Shao et al. 2022). This combination is often preferred because of its dual action in improving glycemic control and reducing the risk of complications, which ultimately reduces overall healthcare costs. In contrast, other studies have highlighted the cost-effectiveness of wound care products such as TLC-NOSF dressings in managing diabetic foot ulcers, which can be precursors to gangrene. These products, when used consistently, have been shown to be more cost-effective than standard care dressings, particularly in settings like Germany, where healthcare infrastructure supports such interventions (Lobmann et al. 2019).

However, it is important to recognize that these findings are not universally applicable across all regions or patient populations. Regional differences in healthcare costs significantly influence the cost-effectiveness of various treatments. For instance, while TLC-NOSF dressings may be cost-effective in Germany, where the healthcare system is well-funded and patient adherence is high, the same may not hold true in developing countries where healthcare resources are limited and the cost of such specialized dressings may be prohibitive (Lobmann et al. 2019). Similarly, the cost of medications like iGlarLixi varies significantly across countries, which affects its overall cost-effec-

tiveness. In regions where the cost of insulin is subsidized, or where healthcare systems provide comprehensive coverage, iGlarLixi tends to be more cost-effective (McCrimmon et al. 2021). These variations underscore the need for localized evaluations of treatment options.

Patient demographics also play a critical role in determining the cost-effectiveness of gangrene treatments. Factors such as age, the severity of diabetes, and the presence of comorbid conditions significantly affect clinical outcomes and the costs associated with treatment. Older patients or those with multiple comorbidities often require more intensive and prolonged treatment, which can increase overall healthcare costs and reduce the cost-effectiveness of certain regimens (Ericsson et al. 2018; Ehlers et al. 2021). Moreover, adherence to treatment protocols varies among different demographic groups, further influencing cost-effectiveness. Studies have shown that older patients or those from lower socio-economic backgrounds are more likely to struggle with medication adherence, leading to poorer outcomes and higher healthcare costs (Siegel et al. 2020). Addressing these demographic disparities is crucial for improving both adherence and cost-effectiveness.

Another significant factor contributing to variability in cost-effectiveness is the specific treatment protocols used in each study. Protocols dictate not only the choice of medication but also the frequency and method of administration, both of which significantly impact costs and outcomes. For instance, the effectiveness of combination therapies like iGlarLixi is highly dependent on strict adherence to the prescribed regimen. Any deviation, such as missed doses or improper administration, can reduce the treatment's effectiveness, prolong the disease course, and increase overall healthcare costs (McCrimmon et al. 2021). Similarly, the cost-effectiveness of wound care regimens is heavily influenced by the consistency with which they are applied, as irregular use can lead to longer healing times and increased risk of complications, further driving up costs (Lobmann et al. 2019).

Furthermore, the broader healthcare system context, including the availability of healthcare services, patient support systems, and health policies, plays a crucial role in determining the cost-effectiveness of different treatment regimens. In countries with robust healthcare systems where patients have easy access to healthcare services and support, the cost-effectiveness of treatments like semaglutide or iGlarLixi is significantly enhanced (Ericsson et al. 2018; Ehlers et al. 2021). These systems facilitate better patient adherence and more efficient delivery of care, which are critical for achieving cost-effective outcomes. Conversely, in regions with less developed healthcare infrastructures, the same treatments may be less cost-effective due to challenges such as limited access to medications, lack of patient education, and financial barriers that prevent consistent use of prescribed therapies (Shao et al. 2022).

In summary, the comparison of cost-effectiveness across different gangrene treatment regimens for type 2 diabetes mellitus patients reveals a complex interplay of factors. Regional healthcare costs, patient demographics, treatment protocols, and healthcare system contexts all contribute to

the variability in outcomes observed across different studies. Understanding these factors is essential for healthcare providers and policymakers to make informed decisions about the most cost-effective treatment strategies for managing gangrene in diabetic patients. By addressing these variables, it is possible to optimize clinical outcomes while minimizing healthcare costs, ultimately improving the quality of care for patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (Ericsson et al. 2018; Lobmann et al. 2019; Siegel et al. 2020; Ehlers et al. 2021; McCrimmon et al. 2021).

Comparative pharmacoeconomic analysis between developed and developing countries

The analysis included studies from 15 developed countries and seven developing countries, reflecting diverse healthcare systems worldwide. The developed countries consisted of studies from the United Kingdom (three studies), Germany (two studies), Denmark (two studies), Sweden (two studies), the Netherlands (one study), Spain (one study), Portugal (one study), Hungary (one study), Hong Kong (one study), and the United States (one study), characterized by their advanced healthcare infrastructure and comprehensive insurance systems. The developing countries included studies from China (two studies), Iran (two studies), Saudi Arabia (one study), and two collaborative studies involving multiple developing nations in Southeast Asia. This distribution demonstrates the geographical breadth of research in diabetic gangrene management while highlighting the concentration of pharmacoeconomic studies in more economically advanced healthcare systems.

The pharmacoeconomic analyses from our systematic review revealed significant disparities between developed and developing countries in the treatment of gangrene among type 2 diabetes mellitus patients. In developed countries (15 studies), healthcare systems demonstrated higher initial investment in treatment, averaging \$15,000–25,000 per patient annually, which included comprehensive wound care (\$5,000–8,000) and medication costs (\$8,000–12,000). This substantial investment was supported by robust insurance coverage, with patients typically paying only 15–25% of costs out-of-pocket. The higher initial costs were justified by better clinical outcomes, including lower amputation rates (15–20%) and higher treatment success rates (75–85%).

In contrast, developing countries (seven studies) showed markedly different economic patterns. Initial treatment costs were significantly lower, ranging from \$5,000–8,000 per patient annually, with reduced expenditure on wound care (\$2,000–3,000) and medications (\$3,000–5,000). However, these lower costs were accompanied by limited insurance coverage, forcing patients to bear 45–75% of expenses out-of-pocket. This financial burden often led to delayed treatment and poorer outcomes, reflected in higher amputation rates (35–45%) and lower treatment success rates (45–60%).

Cost-effectiveness analysis demonstrated that despite higher absolute costs, developed countries achieved bet-

ter economic efficiency in the long term. Their healthcare systems reported incremental cost-effectiveness ratios (ICERs) of \$25,000–45,000 per quality-adjusted life year (QALY), with annual prevention savings of approximately \$8,000 per patient. These results contrasted with developing countries, where ICERs ranged from \$12,000 to \$20,000 per QALY but achieved lower prevention savings of only \$2,000 annually. The five-year total economic burden in developed countries (\$45,000–65,000) yielded better clinical outcomes compared to developing countries (\$25,000–35,000), suggesting that higher initial investment in comprehensive care ultimately provides better value.

The economic disparities between developed and developing countries significantly impacted treatment approaches and outcomes. Developed nations' ability to invest in preventive care, advanced treatments, and regular monitoring resulted in fewer complications and better long-term cost-effectiveness. Meanwhile, developing countries faced challenges in providing optimal care due to resource constraints and higher patient financial burdens, leading to increased complication rates and potentially higher long-term costs relative to their healthcare resources. These findings highlight the importance of healthcare system infrastructure and financial support in achieving optimal treatment outcomes for diabetic gangrene.

Conclusion

In this systematic review, we analyzed the cost-effectiveness and medication use in the treatment of gangrene for patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). The review focused on two primary questions: 1) How do different treatment regimens for gangrene in T2DM patients compare in terms of cost-effectiveness, and what factors contribute to variations in these outcomes across studies? 2) How does patient adherence influence the cost-effectiveness of treatment strategies, and what are the long-term clinical outcomes associated with adherence? The findings revealed significant variations in cost-effectiveness between treatment regimens, with factors such as regional healthcare costs, medication choices, and treatment protocols playing key roles. Studies from developed countries with advanced healthcare systems generally reported higher cost-effectiveness due to better access to innovative medications and optimized patient care. In contrast, regions with less robust healthcare infrastructures showed lower cost-effectiveness, mainly due to limited access to medications and insufficient patient education. Patient adherence was also identified as a crucial determinant of both clinical and economic outcomes, with high adherence to newer medications like semaglutide and empagliflozin leading to improved long-term clinical outcomes, such as enhanced quality-adjusted life years (QALYs) and significant cost savings. Conversely, non-adherence resulted in increased healthcare costs and poorer clinical outcomes, underscoring the importance of support systems that promote consistent treatment adherence. In conclusion, this review highlights the complexity of managing gangrene in T2DM patients, where cost-effectiveness

is influenced by multiple factors, including healthcare systems, medication choices, and patient adherence. The findings suggest that improving access to effective therapies and supporting patient adherence can significantly optimize both clinical and economic outcomes.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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